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**An extended pressure range
comparison of the blower door and
novel pulse method for measuring
the airtightness of two outdoor
chambers with different levels of
airtightness**

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Introduction

Equipment and setup

Test results

Conclusions

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The pulse technique is implemented by releasing a measured amount of compressed air over short period of time (1.5 s) to the test space and monitor the pressure response in the space.

Tank unit

Compressor motor

Pressure transducer

Air tank (10 bar)

Solenoid valve

Control unit

Test chamber

Pod	1: Standard	2: Passivhaus
Volume (m ³)	21	22
Envelope area (m ²)	47	48
Approximate ACH @50Pa	6	1.65

BD-4

PULSE-20

Unsealed

Sealed

Results-Standard

- The gaps between the blower door and door frame were responsible for a significant proportion of the overall air leakage in this test arrangement when the door/ blower door interface was not over sealed. (up to 30% for Pod 1 and up to 60% for Pod 2).
- In the scenario where the door frames were sealed, Pod 1, which has an airtightness level typical of new build dwellings in the UK, has shown good agreement of results between the pulse and blower methods, circa <13% deviation across the range. Pod 2 gave less agreement than in Pod 1; circa <42% maximum but much better than the scenario where the door frames were unsealed.
- It was found in testing that the pulse created in Pod 2 was unlike that seen in average dwellings, which was caused by the fact that in this highly airtight pod it took longer for the pressure pulse to peak and hence a range of data that is closer to the peak was captured for analysis i.e. the elevated pressure persisted for a prolonged period following the cessation of air from the pulse unit. Further testing in this field will look at the behaviour of pulse i.e. pulse shape in the highly air tight environments and how this may affect the results.

Many thanks!

Any queries:

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